

Synthesis, spectral characterization, catalytic and biological studies of new Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes containing N₂O donor ligands

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Abstract : A series of ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes of the type [RuCl(CO)(B)(L)] (where B = PPh₃/AsPh₃/py/pip; L = monobasic tridentate Schiff base ligands) were synthesized and characterized. These complexes catalyze oxidation of alcohols with up to 64.17% in the presence of *N*-methyl morpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO) as co-oxidant. Furthermore, *in vitro* toxicity of these complexes was tested against the growth of bacterial species viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Salmonella typhi*. An octahedral structure has been proposed for all of the new complexes.

Keywords : Ruthenium(II) Schiff base complexes, characterization, catalytic oxidation, antibacterial activity.

Introduction

The chemistry of ruthenium complexes with nitrogen containing ligands has been extensively studied in recent years¹. Ruthenium(II) complexes have served as a selective antimetastatic agents², as anticancer drugs against³⁻⁵ colorectal tumors. Here the interactions between ruthenium complexes have gained interest in a number of complexes of adenine⁶, hypoxanthine^{7,8} and guanine^{9,10} derivatives have been structurally described in which nitrogen coordination is most frequently observed. Transition metal complexes of ruthenium have proved to be useful catalyst in many reactions such as oxidation, hydrogenation, carbonylation and hydroformylation by virtue of the accessibility of ruthenium in different oxidation states and ease of coordination with different ligands¹¹⁻¹³. Tridentate Schiff base ligands have been successfully used in several catalytic asymmetric reactions^{14,15}. Metal complexes of ruthenium containing triphenylphosphine or arsine, nitrogen and oxygen donor atoms are found to be effective catalysts for oxidation reactions^{16,17}. In particular, the selective oxidation of alcohols into carbonyl compounds by metal complexes are well documented in the literature¹⁸⁻²⁰. Sharples *et al.*²¹ carried out a yield based study on oxidation of geranial, etc., catalyzed by ruthenium in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO) and *N,N*-dimethylaniline-*N*-oxide. There are few reports available on the oxidation of carbonyl compounds

by using NMO as co-oxidant. In this paper, we report the synthesis, spectral, catalytic and biological activities of ruthenium(II) tridentate Schiff base complexes containing triphenylphosphine/arsine. The general structure of the Schiff base ligands used in this study is given in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Structure of Schiff base ligands.

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

The Schiff bases were prepared in 80–90% yield by condensation of two mole equivalents of salicylaldehyde, phenylenediamine and respective aldehyde or ketone by following the reported procedure²². Solvents were purified and dried according to the standard procedures²³. RuCl₃·3H₂O purchased from Loba Chemie, was used without further purification. The starting complexes [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₃]²⁴, [RuHCl(CO)(AsPh₃)₃]²⁵, [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(py)]²⁶ and [RuHCl(CO)(PPh₃)₂(pip)]²⁶ were pre-

pared by reported literature methods.

Physical measurements :

The analysis of carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed on a Carlo Erba 1160 and a model 240 Perkin-Elmer CHN analyzer at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, India. IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} region in a Nicolet Avater model FT-IR spectrophotometer. Electronic spectra were recorded on a Systronic 119 UV-Vis spectrophotometer using CH_2Cl_2 solution. ^1H NMR and ^{31}P NMR spectra were recorded on a Burkert 400 MHz instrument using TMS and orthophosphoric acid as an internal standard reference.

Preparation of the new Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes :

All the new complexes were prepared by the following general procedure. To a solution of $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{B})]$ (where $\text{B} = \text{PPh}_3$, py (or) pip) and $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)_3]$ (0.10 mmol) in benzene, appropriate Schiff base (0.1 mmol) was added and heated under reflux for 5 h. The resulting solution was concentrated to 3 cm^3 and cooled. Petroleum ether (60–80 $^\circ\text{C}$) (5 cm^3) was then added whereupon the complex separated out. The solid was filtered off, washed and recrystallized from CH_2Cl_2 /petroleum ether mixture and dried *in vacuo*.

Results and discussion

Light and air stable ruthenium(II) complexes of the general formula $[\text{Ru}(\text{CO})(\text{EPh}_3)(\text{B})(\text{L})]$ ($\text{E} = \text{P}$ or As ; $\text{B} = \text{PPh}_3$ or AsPh_3 or py or pip; $\text{L} =$ monobasic or tridentate Schiff base) have been prepared by reacting $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{EPh}_3)_2(\text{B})]$ with the respective Schiff bases in 1 : 1 molar ratio in benzene (Scheme 2).

All the complexes are green in colour. The analytical data obtained for the new complexes (Table 1) agree very well with the proposed molecular formulae in all of the above reactions. The Schiff bases behaved as monobasic tridentate ligands. The new products obtained from the reaction of $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)_3]$ with Schiff base ligands contained two triphenylphosphine moieties on ruthenium ion, whereas the corresponding reactions of $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ or $[\text{RuHCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{PPh}_3)_2]$ with Schiff base ligands yielded new complexes with only one triphenylphosphine ligand on ruthenium ion. These observations do indicate a more labile nature of $\text{Ru}-\text{P}$ bond compared to the $\text{Ru}-\text{N}$ bond of the heterocyclic

Scheme 2. Structure of Ru^{II} Schiff base complexes.

nitrogen bases to the ruthenium ion. The difference in the strength of $\text{Ru}-\text{P}$ and $\text{Ru}-\text{N}$ bonds may be explained as on the basis of better σ donating ability of the nitrogen bases compared to that of triphenylphosphine.

IR spectral studies :

The $\nu(\text{OH})$ band originally found in the Schiff base ligands disappeared on complexation indicating deprotonation of the phenolic hydroxyl group and coordination of phenolic oxygen to the metal. This is further supported by the shift in the stretching frequency of the phenolic $\text{C}-\text{O}$ to the higher side by 30–40 cm^{-1} ²⁷. A strong band was observed at 1620–1600 cm^{-1} in the free ligand which is characteristic of the azomethine $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ group. It is expected that coordination of nitrogen to the metal atom might reduce the electron density in the azomethine link and thus the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretching frequency in the complexes was observed in the region 1585–1599 cm^{-1} indicating coordination of the Schiff bases through azomethine nitrogen²⁸. In addition, other characteristic bands due to PPh_3 and AsPh_3 are also present around 1435 cm^{-1} ²⁹. In the spectra of Schiff base complexes, a medium intensity band observed in the 1020 cm^{-1} region characteristic of the coordinated pyridine or piperidine³⁰. In all the new ruthenium complexes the band due to terminally coordinated $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group appeared at 1900–1944 cm^{-1} ³¹.

Electronic spectral studies :

The electronic absorption spectra of all the complexes

Table 1. Analytical, elemental analysis, infra-red and electronic spectra of Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes

Sl. No.	Complexes	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			IR spectra (cm ⁻¹)		Electronic spectra
		C	H	N	$\nu_{C=N}$	ν_{C-O}	
1.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]	56.02 (56.65)	4.21 (4.06)	4.21 (4.14)	1586	1303	747, 410, 346, 280
2.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ¹)]	52.32 (51.28)	3.93 (3.51)	3.93 (3.64)	1597	1311	739, 402, 281
3.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ¹)]	72.0 (72.78)	4.66 (4.11)	3.00 (2.89)	1584	1311	780, 412, 327, 286
4.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ¹)]	71.88 (70.87)	4.65 (4.11)	3.16 (2.99)	1583	1308	695, 417, 320, 280
5.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]	61.85 (59.18)	4.12 (3.91)	4.12 (3.87)	1586	1307	748, 410, 337, 270
6.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ²)]	56.19 (56.57)	3.85 (3.33)	3.99 (4.12)	1585	1306	740, 406, 260
7.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ²)]	78.17 (78.89)	4.56 (4.92)	3.42 (3.09)	1587	1305	741, 416, 320, 275
8.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ²)]	78.04 (77.01)	4.55 (3.17)	3.57 (2.18)	1533	1306	695, 407, 318, 270
9.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ³)]	64.77 (64.10)	3.77 (3.60)	4.04 (4.00)	1598	1309	697, 406, 336, 260
10.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ³)]	60.91 (58.17)	3.55 (3.51)	3.80 (3.67)	1592	1306	680, 402, 340, 270
11.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ³)]	62.71 (62.70)	4.57 (4.31)	4.12 (3.98)	1597	1345	720, 410, 343
12.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ³)]	76.57 (76.83)	4.54 (4.81)	4.07 (4.75)	1586	1310	737, 417, 340, 265

in dichloromethane showed three to four bands in the region 260–780 nm. All the ruthenium complexes are diamagnetic, indicating the presence of ruthenium in the +2 oxidation state. The ground state of ruthenium(II) in an octahedral environment is $^1A_{1g}$ from the $t_{2g}^6 e_g^1$ configuration, and the excited states corresponding to the $t_{2g}^6 e_g^1$ configuration are $^3T_{1g}$, $^3T_{2g}$, $^1T_{1g}$ and $^1T_{2g}$. Hence, four bands corresponding to the transition $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{1g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^3T_{2g}$, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ are possible in the order of increasing energy.

The bands around 779–589 nm and 485–406 nm are assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ and charge transfer (CT) transitions respectively^{32,33} are listed in Table 2. The charge transfer bands observed in all the complexes due to M \rightarrow L transitions are possible in the visible region^{33–35}. Moreover, the presence of carbonyl, triphenylphosphine/arsine and heterocyclic bases as ligands, which are capable of producing strong ligand field in e_g^* which is in relatively higher energy levels. Therefore the lowest charge bands

due to the excitation of an electron from the metal t_{2g} level to an unfilled π^* molecular orbital of the ligand appeared in the relatively high energy region compared to $t_{2g} \rightarrow e_g^*$ transitions^{34–36}. The other high intensity bands in the 344–269 nm region were characterised by ligand-centered (LC) bands and have been designated as $\pi-\pi^*$ and $n-\pi^*$ transitions for the localized on the azomethine group of the Schiff's base³⁵. The patterns of the electronic spectra of all the complexes indicated the presence of an octahedral environment around the ruthenium(II) ion, similar to that of ruthenium(II) octahedral complexes those have been reported elsewhere³⁷.

¹H NMR spectral studies :

The ligand to metal bonding is further supported by the ¹H NMR spectra (Table 2). All the complexes showed multiplets at 7.0–7.99 ppm range due to the phenyl protons of Schiff base and triphenylphosphine³⁸. In the complexes of [RuCl(CO)(AsPh₃)(L²)] and [RuCl(CO)(PPh₃)(L²)] an extra singlet was found in the region at 2.05 ppm

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR spectrum of [RuCl(CO)(AsPh₃)(L²)].

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR spectrum of [RuCl(CO)(PPh₃)(L²)].

which has been assigned to the extra methyl group present in the Schiff base (Figs. 1 and 2). The azomethine proton signals in the complexes lie in the 8.0–8.65 ppm range. The peak due to the azomethine showed a high field shift compared to the free Schiff base after complexation with the metal ion indicating coordination through the azomethine nitrogen atom³⁹. The complete absence of signals due to the phenolic OH protons in the complexes

suggests deprotonation and coordination of the phenolic oxygen to the metal center³¹. In addition to the above signals resonances corresponding to CH₃ protons are also observed in 1.50 to 1.63 ppm region⁴⁰.

The ³¹P NMR spectra for two of the complexes have

Table 2. ¹H NMR and ³¹P NMR spectra of Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes

Sl. No.	Complexes	¹ H NMR (ppm)	³¹ P NMR (ppm)
1.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]	7.0–7.92 (m, aromatic) 8.42 (s, CH=N) 1.6 (s, CH ₃)	28.72
2.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]	7.3–7.99 (m, aromatic) 8.62 (s, CH=N) 1.6 (s, CH ₃) 2.08 (s, CH ₃)	28.56
3.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ³)]	7.2–7.89 (m, aromatic) 8.61 (s, CH=N) 1.58 (s, CH ₃)	28.65
4.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ¹)]	7.3–7.89 (m, aromatic) 8.56 (s, CH=N) 1.53 (s, CH ₃)	
5.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ²)]	7.43–7.90 (m, aromatic) 8.52 (s, CH=N) 1.56 (s, CH ₃) 2.02 (s, CH ₃)	

Fig. 3. ^{31}P NMR spectrum of $[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{L}^3)]$.Table 3. Catalytic oxidation of alcohols by Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes using *N*-methyl morpholine-*N*-oxide as co-oxidant

Sl. No.	Complexes	Substrate	Product	Yield ^a	Turnover number ^b
1.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{L}^1)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	60.72	63.72
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	33.67	34.16
2.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{L}^1)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	52.65	54.63
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	29.68	30.61
3.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{L}^1)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	57.68	58.17
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	31.65	32.18
4.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{pip})(\text{L}^2)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	59.72	50.17
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	33.67	34.17
5.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{L}^2)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	53.17	64.83
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	34.18	35.19
6.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{L}^2)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	56.67	57.16
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	30.19	31.29
7.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{L}^3)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	64.17	65.18
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	34.92	35.67
8.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{AsPh}_3)(\text{L}^3)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	54.18	57.67
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	30.15	31.28
9.	$[\text{RuCl}(\text{CO})(\text{py})(\text{L}^3)]$	Benzylalcohol	Benzaldehyde	57.63	59.16
		Cyclohexanol	Cyclohexanone	32.67	33.17

^aYields based on substrate; ^bMoles of product per mole of catalyst.

been recorded in order to confirm the presence of triphenylphosphine groups and to determine the geometry of the complexes (Table 3, Fig. 3). The appear-

ance of a singlet around 28.65–28.72 ppm in the spectrum of complexes confirmed the presence of one triphenylphosphine group.

Catalytic studies :

The oxidation of benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol using the different ruthenium complexes as catalysts in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide (NMO) as co-oxidant were carried out in dichloromethane. The results of the catalytic oxidation by ruthenium(II) complexes are summarised in Table 4. Benzaldehyde was formed from benzyl alcohol and cyclohexanol was converted into cyclohexanone after 3 h of stirring at room temperature. The aldehyde/ketone formed were quantified as their 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone derivatives. In no case there was any detectable oxidation of alcohols in the presence of *N*-methylmorpholine-*N*-oxide alone without the ruthenium

showed less catalytic activity when compared to other complexes, which could be attributed to the presence of the electron donating methyl group in these complexes which decreases the catalytic activity by increasing the electron density on the metal ion⁴³.

Antibacterial studies :

The *in vitro* antibacterial screening of the ligands and their ruthenium complexes have been carried out against *Escherichia coli*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Salmonella typhi* using a nutrient agar medium by disc diffusion method. The results (Table 4) showed the complexes exhibit moderate activity against *Escherichia coli*, *Aeromonas hydrophila* and *Salmonella typhi*. The toxicity of ruthenium

Table 4. Antibacterial studies of Ru^{II} carbonyl Schiff base complexes

Sl. No.	Ligand/Complexes	Diameter of inhibition zones (mm)								
		<i>Escherichia coli</i> (%)			<i>Aeromonas hydrophila</i> (%)			<i>Salmonella typhi</i> (%)		
		0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.5	1	0.25	0.5	1
1.	L ¹	9	10	12	10	11	12	8	11	12
2.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ¹)]	10	12	14	12	16	19	12	15	19
3.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ¹)]	11	14	15	14	17	20	13	15	20
4.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ¹)]	13	15	18	14	17	20	15	17	19
5.	L ²	9	11	13	8	11	13	9	10	12
6.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ²)]	11	14	20	10	13	15	13	14	18
7.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ²)]	13	16	19	12	18	20	15	16	18
8.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ²)]	14	17	21	14	20	22	19	20	22
9.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ²)]	15	18	20	15	17	21	20	21	22
10.	L ³	10	12	13	11	13	14	9	11	12
11.	[RuCl(CO)(PPh ₃)(L ³)]	12	14	17	14	16	18	15	18	20
12.	[RuCl(CO)(AsPh ₃)(L ³)]	14	18	20	15	18	20	17	18	21
13.	[RuCl(CO)(pip)(L ³)]	16	17	21	15	17	21	20	22	23
14.	[RuCl(CO)(py)(L ³)]	17	18	20	16	18	20	20	23	24
15.	<i>Streptomycin</i>	22	23	28	21	27	29	29	21	25

complexes. All the synthesised ruthenium complexes were found to catalyse the oxidation of alcohols to aldehydes/ketones but the yields and the turnover were found to vary with different catalysts. The relatively higher product yield obtained for the oxidation of benzyl alcohol than for cyclohexanol is due to the fact that the α -CH moiety of benzyl alcohol is more acidic than in cyclohexanol⁴¹. It has also been found that triphenylphosphine complexes possess higher catalytic activity than the triphenylarsine complexes⁴². This may be due to the higher donor ability of the arsine ligand compared to that of phosphines. It has also been found that ruthenium(II) complexes derived from 4 (*N*) methyl phenylidindiimine ligands

increase on increasing the concentration⁴⁴. The increase in the antibacterial activity of the metal chelates may be due to the effect of the metal ion on the normal cell process. A possible mode of the toxicity increase may be considered in light of Tweedys chelation theory⁴⁵. Chelation considerably reduces the polarity of the metal ion because of partial sharing of its positive charge with the donor groups and possible π -electron delocalization over the whole chelate ring. Such chelation could enhance the lyophilic character of central metal atom, which subsequently favours its permeation through the lipid layers of cell membrane. Furthermore, the mode of action of the compounds may involve formation of a

hydrogen bond through the azomethine ($>C=N$) group with the active centers of cell constituents, resulting in the interference of normal cell processes⁴⁶. Though the complexes possess activity they could not reach the effectiveness of the standard drug *Streptomycin*. The variation in the effectiveness of the different compounds against different organism depend either on the impermeability of the cells or the microbe of difference in ribosome of microbial cells⁴⁷.

Thus, based on the analytical, spectral (IR, electronic, ¹H NMR and ³¹P NMR) data, an octahedral structure (Scheme 2) has been tentatively proposed for all new ruthenium(II) complexes.

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